

Sample Name: PVC UV 1-5 μm

Material: Polyvinyl Chloride

Size: 1-5 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 3,95 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $2,6 \times 10^{12}$ particles per gram
- 18369 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C_2ClH_3 (PVC) determined by XRF
- C=O peak (1722 cm^{-1}) due to oxidation observed in FTIR spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PVC spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
4,42	2,37	0,73	0,31	0,21	3,95	2.6×10^{12}	18369

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C_2ClH_3	99,81
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Na	36
Al	443
Si	281
P	51
S	709
Ca	45
Cr	66
Fe	167
Ni	12
Cu	3
Zn	4
Mo	4

Chemical Bonding (Using $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

